

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

**EXPLORE MORE
USE CASES**

From Data to Decisions: DTO-BioFlow Use Cases

DUC 4 - Delivering evidence-based knowledge to support spatial planning of sustainable mariculture."

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From Insight to Impact

The Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) are at the heart of the DTO-BioFlow initiative, translating complex scientific capabilities into tangible digital solutions for marine biodiversity monitoring and management.

Designed to showcase the power of an **end-to-end digital approach**, these use cases connect cutting-edge biodiversity observations with AI-enhanced models, analytical tools, and the infrastructure of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Each DUC serves as a living example of how real-world marine challenges can be addressed through integrated digital workflows. They all address a pressing challenge for ocean sustainability and proposes an integrated, evidence-based solution.

DUC 4 focuses on the spatial planning of sustainable mariculture.

Aquaculture is a rapidly expanding sector with high potential for sustainable food production, but it must be carefully managed to avoid environmental harm. This use case supports **data-driven spatial planning for mariculture** by integrating environmental, biological, and eDNA data to identify optimal farm sites, minimize ecological risks, and promote ecosystem-based aquaculture.

Challenge

Sustainable mariculture lacks reliable planning tools.

Uncertainty around site suitability, biomass yield, and species interactions limits the adoption of low-impact, multi-trophic systems and increases operational risk.

Solution

This DUC develops predictive tools for smarter site selection.

By combining monitoring data, remote sensing, and eDNA, it models species impacts, forecasts yield, and supports climate-resilient mariculture planning.

Data and monitoring networks used

Monitoring data, environmental data, eDNA data, Remote sensing products and climate projections.

Expected Outputs

Site-specific models

Predictive tools

Planning support for low-impact aquaculture development

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Scenario simulation:** Tests climate and management options for mariculture performance
- **Risk forecasting:** Anticipates harmful species effects at specific sites
- **Data integration:** Combines genomic, environmental, and observational data for planning

Useful for

- Aquaculture operators
- Marine spatial planners
- Regulatory agencies

Learn more on development and read the publications

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Consortium

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